

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON BRAND SATISFACTION AND BRAND LOYALTY OF WARDAH BRAND COSMETIC PRODUCTS WITH CUSTOMER BRAND ENGAGEMENT AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE ON THE INSTAGRAM PLATFORM

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of social media marketing on brand satisfaction and brand loyalty of Wardah cosmetic products with customer brand engagement as a mediating variable on the Instagram platform. The data in this study were 165 consumers of Wardah cosmetic products. Data collection in this study used a questionnaire with data analysis tools using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) operated by the Amos device. The results of the study indicate that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on customer brand engagement, customer brand satisfaction, and brand loyalty. Then, customer brand engagement has a positive and significant effect on customer brand satisfaction and brand loyalty. And the mediation effect test found that customer brand engagement is a partial mediating variable between social media marketing and brand satisfaction and brand loyalty. The results of this study are expected to provide important contributions for stakeholders in developing cosmetic product marketing strategies and customer understanding of products and brands.

Keywords: *Social Media Marketing, Brand Satisfaction, Brand Loyalty, Customer Brand Engagement, Cosmetic Product.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapidly growing cosmetics industry has given rise to new brands, each with its own unique characteristics. Competition in the cosmetics industry is becoming increasingly fierce due to the emergence of new brands. Each cosmetics company has a different marketing strategy, one of which is a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) marketing strategy, specifically highlighting the product's strengths (Misadiwana et al., 2024). One example is the local brand Wardah, which consistently releases innovative cosmetic products. Over the past decade, social media platforms worldwide have seen tremendous growth. Instagram, in particular, has become a dominant platform for sharing visual content with a large user base. Instagram has become a staple for businesses promoting their products and services. Features like direct messaging, search and explore, short videos, digital filters, tagging, commenting, and linking have made it easier for businesses to connect with their customers and potential customers, making it a highly effective marketing tool. This has led to the emergence of numerous industry-specific and social media-based campaigns that utilize Instagram as their primary marketing tool (Chakti, 2019). In Indonesia, Instagram's growth has been significant in recent years. It is the most widely used social media platform in Indonesia, with 80% of the country's total internet users using the platform (Wirayudha et al., 2023). This high level of user engagement has made many businesses realize the importance of Instagram as a primary tool for marketing and promoting their products.

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Figure 1 Number of Social Media Platform Users in Indonesia (2024)

Source: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-indonesia>

The results of the Hootsuite survey published by datareportal.com (2024) Data shows that 85.3% of the population uses Instagram in Indonesia. This data demonstrates that, in addition to WhatsApp, Instagram is a popular social media platform among Indonesians, enabling it to support various economic transactions, such as marketing activities. According to Chaudhary (2021), Instagram has become a new and effective marketing tool in social media marketing, with many businesses realizing its potential to help promote their products and services. Wardah is one of the leading local cosmetics brands in Indonesia that strategically utilizes the Instagram social media platform as a means to strengthen its brand image, expand market reach, and build emotional closeness with millennial and generation Z consumers. This activity reflects the company's efforts to build customer brand engagement through active consumer participation, such as commenting, liking, sharing content, and participating in digital campaigns. However, the effectiveness of this social media marketing strategy in increasing brand loyalty still requires empirical evidence. It is not yet known for certain the extent to which social media marketing practices are able to influence brand satisfaction and ultimately contribute to the formation of customer loyalty to the brand. Brand loyalty refers to a consumer's willingness to purchase and recommend a brand (Sun et al., 2024). However, some cosmetic brands require more accurate and sustainable marketing strategies, so that they can influence consumers in building stable brand loyalty, along with increasing market competition and diverse consumer preferences, maintaining consumer loyalty is becoming increasingly complex (Wilson et al., 2024).

Previous research shows that marketing activities on social media can influence perceptions of brand value, trust, and attachment which in turn increases customer loyalty (A. Liu & Jin, 2025; X. Liu et al., 2025; Muchardie et al., 2023; Rugati & Santoso, 2025). However, the causal relationship between the variables of social media marketing, customer brand engagement, brand satisfaction, and brand loyalty still shows varying results depending on the cultural context and industry characteristics (Suwandi & Balqiah, 2023). Therefore, this research is important to examine in depth the relationship between these variables in the context of the rapidly growing Indonesian local cosmetics industry. The urgency of this research is also reinforced by the high level of competition in the cosmetics industry in Indonesia as well as changes in consumer behavior that are increasingly digitalized. According to Muchardie et al., (2023), The level of brand engagement on social media significantly influences customer loyalty to local cosmetic brands, but the mediating effect of brand satisfaction has rarely been comprehensively tested. Therefore, a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of social media's influence on brand loyalty will provide theoretical contributions to the development of digital marketing literature, while also providing practical implications for communication and promotion strategies of local cosmetic brands in the digital economy era.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

The Relationship Between Social Media Marketing and Customer Brand Engagement

Social media platforms provide an interactive space to convey information that is entertaining, engaging and relevant, thereby encouraging customers' cognitive engagement with the brand (Ashley & Tuten, 2019; Barger et al., 2016). Research shows that SMM dimensions, such as *entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, dan electronic word of mouth* (e-WOM), plays an important role in increasing customer brand engagement (CBE) because it is able to attract customer attention, stimulate positive responses, and strengthen brand perceptions (Kim & Ko, 2020; Vukasović, 2019). Trending topics and real-time information updates also strengthen customers' cognitive and emotional presence, creating a more meaningful brand experience and driving loyalty (Chan et al., 2014; Unnava & Aravindakshan, 2021). This kind of interaction has been shown to increase customer trust, satisfaction, and the tendency to continue following brand developments (Harrigan et al., 2017; Laroche et al., 2013). Meanwhile, e-WOM expands the spread of credible opinions and recommendations, builds emotional closeness, and creates positive brand experiences among customers (Shafiq et al., 2023). Overall, the combination of informative, interactive, personal, and shareable content is the main foundation in strengthening the relationship between social media marketing and customer brand engagement (Dessart, 2017). Based on the description above regarding the relationship between social media marketing and customer brand engagement from an empirical perspective, the hypothesis in this study is:

H₁: SMM has a significant influence on the CBE of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform.

The Relationship Between Social Media Marketing and Brand Satisfaction

Social Media Marketing through E-WOM elements also correlates with consumer satisfaction. Fakhira et al., (2024), In their study on the Shopee platform, they found that e-WOM factors (such as the number and credibility of reviews) influence consumer satisfaction, which in turn impacts purchasing decisions. Several empirical studies have shown that SMM activities, such as interactive content, regular posting, and active engagement with followers, have a positive and significant impact on consumer satisfaction. For example, Uthman & Marie, (2025) found that social media marketing activities directly influence respondents' commitment, trust, and satisfaction. Furthermore, a recent literature review found that dimensions of Social Media Marketing Activities (SMMA) such as interaction, entertainment, and promotion emerged as key themes influencing customer response and satisfaction (Bakalo, 2024). Quantitative research on Indonesian e-commerce platforms also shows that SMM has a significant effect on brand trust, and this trust further contributes to customer satisfaction (Walean et al., 2025). As well as, Chen & Lin, (2019), stated that brand trust has been shown to play a significant role in linking SMM with customer satisfaction and loyalty among active users of e-commerce platforms. Based on the above description of the relationship between social media marketing and brand satisfaction from an empirical perspective, the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H₂: SMM has a significant influence on the BS of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform.

The Relationship Between Social Media Marketing and Customer Brand Loyalty

Social Media Marketing (SMM) has proven to be a key driver of brand loyalty. Recent research shows that social media marketing activities, such as interaction, entertainment, promotions, and word-of-mouth, can build customer engagement and brand trust, which together strengthen consumers' long-term bonds with the brand (Ebrahim, 2019; Khusniah & Astuti, 2024). Furthermore, several studies have shown that the influence of SMM on brand loyalty is often indirect and mediated by variables such as brand trust and brand equity. For example, a study at Bank Syariah Indonesia found that SMM does not always directly influence loyalty, but its effect becomes significant through the mediation of brand trust and brand equity (Amri & Ariyanti, 2023). Meanwhile, research in the F&B industry (Indomie products) shows that SMM has a significant impact on consumer loyalty, but only through brand experience as a mediator (Novia & Loisa, 2024). Thus, an effective SMM strategy focuses not only on content and reach but also on building trust and meaningful brand experiences. This approach strengthens consumers' emotional and cognitive bonds with the brand, which can strengthen loyalty and retain customers in the long term. Based on the above description of the relationship between social media marketing and brand loyalty from an empirical perspective, the hypothesis in this study is:

H₃: SMM has a significant influence on the BL of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform.

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The Relationship Between Customer Brand Engagement and Customer Brand Satisfaction

Customer Brand Engagement (CBE) is consumer involvement with a brand that encompasses cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions and has been shown to be an important factor in shaping brand satisfaction. Research by Tuti & Sulistia, (2022), showed that CBE has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction, which then impacts brand trust and loyalty. In their structural model, consumer engagement not only has a direct effect, but also an indirect effect through increased satisfaction as a mediator, reinforcing the importance of engagement as a pillar of long-term brand relationships (Lestari & Syah, 2022). In addition to direct relationships, CBE can strengthen brand satisfaction through other mediating mechanisms such as brand experience and brand attachment. A banking study (Octavia, 2023) found that CBE in mobile banking apps strengthens brand satisfaction through the experience of interacting with the app (Octavia & Azizah, 2023; Rimadias et al., 2021). These findings confirm that when consumers are actively engaged, for example through the use of apps, digital interactions, or relevant content, they tend to experience higher levels of satisfaction with the brand, as engagement increases perceived value and fulfillment of expectations (Li et al., 2020). Based on the description above regarding the relationship between brand engagement and brand satisfaction from an empirical perspective, the hypothesis in this study is

H₄: CBE has a significant influence on the BS of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform.

The Relationship Between Customer Brand Engagement and Customer Brand Loyalty

Customer Brand Engagement (CBE), namely consumer involvement with a brand through cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions and has a positive and significant influence on brand loyalty. Research by (Chairunnisa & Ruswanti, 2023), revealed that CBE drives brand attachment and customer trust, both of which then strengthen brand loyalty. This suggests that consumers who actively interact with brands (e.g., through communities, social media, or interactive content) are more likely to develop emotional bonds and trust through these two key pillars in building long-term loyalty. A study by Susanti et al., (2021), showed that brand satisfaction mediates the effect of CBE on loyalty, meaning that consumer engagement strengthens their satisfaction with the brand, and this satisfaction ultimately drives loyalty. Furthermore, other research (in the context of mobile banking applications) also found that CBE strengthens brand experience, which then increases loyalty through trust (Octavia & Azizah, 2023; Wijaya & Simamora, 2023). This confirms that marketing strategies aimed at increasing engagement are not sufficient through surface interactions alone; companies need to build strong trust by providing consistency, transparency, and responsiveness so that consumer engagement truly translates into long-term loyalty. Based on the above description, the hypothesis in this study is:

H₅: CBE has a positive and significant effect on BL of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform.

The Relationship between Social Media Marketing and Brand Satisfaction through Customer Brand Engagement as a Mediating Variable

Social Media Marketing (SMM) plays a crucial role in shaping brand satisfaction by providing consumers with informative, interactive, and relevant digital experiences. SMM activities such as entertainment content, two-way interactions, product information, and participatory campaigns have been shown to enhance consumers' perceived value and positive brand experiences. Contemporary research shows that SMM can directly enhance brand satisfaction, but this influence is even stronger when it involves consumer engagement as part of the digital interaction process (Lim et al., 2022; Hajmalek et al., 2024). Meanwhile, Customer Brand Engagement (CBE) serves as a crucial mechanism bridging the influence of SMM on brand satisfaction. When consumers frequently interact with brand content on social media, for example by commenting, liking posts, sharing content, or participating in digital communities, this engagement creates emotional and cognitive experiences that deepen their relationship with the brand. Recent studies have shown that SMM significantly increases CBE, which in turn fuels brand satisfaction because consumers feel engaged, cared for, and have a stronger connection to the brand (Bakalo, 2024; Tuti & Sulistia, 2022). As a mediating variable, CBE strengthens the relationship between SMM and brand satisfaction by transforming passive marketing activities into interactive experiences. Recent research has found that CBE's mediating role is significant in various contexts, such as services, retail, and digital platforms, indicating that the higher the engagement generated by social media marketing activities, the greater the impact on brand satisfaction (Octavia & Azizah, 2023; Walean et al., 2025). Thus, CBE serves as a psychological bridge that transforms digital interactions into brand satisfaction. Based on the above description, the hypothesis in this study is:

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H₆ : SMM influences the BS of Wardah brand cosmetic products on the Instagram platform through CBE as a mediating variable.

The Relationship between Social Media Marketing and Brand Loyalty through Customer Brand Engagement as a Mediating Variable

Social Media Marketing (SMM) has become a key strategy for building long-term relationships between companies and consumers. SMM activities, such as informative content, two-way interactions, entertainment, and participatory campaigns, can increase consumers' perceived value, emotional closeness, and positive experiences with brands. Several recent studies have shown that SMM has a significant influence on brand loyalty, although the direct effect tends to be weak without psychological variables strengthening the relationship (Lim et al., 2022; Hajmalek et al., 2024). This suggests that SMM essentially provides a foundation for communication and experiences, but consumer loyalty is formed through a deeper process. Empirical studies show that SMM strongly increases CBE, and this engagement then fosters loyalty through a sense of connection, meaningful experiences, and perceived value towards the brand (Tuti & Sulistia, 2022; Susanti et al., 2022). The mediating role of CBE is also supported by research stating that loyalty is formed through an engagement process that creates brand trust, brand satisfaction, and brand attachment. When SMM creates a consistent and enjoyable experience, consumers become more engaged, then feel satisfaction and trust that encourages them to continue choosing, recommending, and repurchasing the brand. Research in the digital and e-commerce industry over the past few years has found that CBE is a significant mediator in the relationship between SMM and brand loyalty, making engagement a crucial element in converting digital interactions into sustainable customer loyalty (Walean et al., 2025; Bakalo & Chalchissa, 2024). Based on the description above, the hypothesis in this study is:

H₇: SMM influences BL of Wardah brand cosmetic products on Instagram platform through CBE as a mediating variable.

METHOD

This study uses an associative research design with a quantitative approach that aims to analyze the relationship between social media marketing and customer brand engagement and its influence on customer brand satisfaction and customer brand loyalty of Wardah cosmetic products in Lhokseumawe City. The quantitative approach was chosen because it allows for objective and accurate measurement of the relationship between variables. The population in this study were consumers or users of Wardah cosmetic products. The number of samples used was 165 respondents, which was determined based on the formula (Hair et al., 2021), by considering the minimum requirements of the statistical analysis used. The sampling technique used purposive sampling involving respondents who have direct experience as users of Wardah cosmetic products. The research data consists of primary data collected through questionnaires using a five-point Likert scale to test the research hypothesis. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling based on Analysis of Moment Structures (SEM-AMOS). SEM is a combination of two statistical concepts, namely factor analysis in the measurement model and regression analysis in the structural model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section systematically explains the results of the research data analysis, including the results of the respondent characteristics analysis, the results of data validity and reliability tests, and the results of the regression weight to assess the form of influence between research variables.

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1 explains the characteristics of respondents in this study grouped based on the number of visits, gender, age, education level, and type of work of the respondents.

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Table 1 Respondent Characteristics

Gender	Amount	Percent
Female	165	100,0
Total	165	100,0
Age	Amount	Percent
< 20 Years	9	5,5
20 - 30 Years	37	22,4
30 - 40 Years	63	38,2
40 - 50 Years	49	29,7
> 50 Years	7	4,2
Total	165	100,0
Marital status	Amount	Percent
Marry	128	77,6
Not Married	37	22,4
Total	165	100,0
Educational level	Amount	Percent
High school or equivalent	56	33,9
Diploma	31	18,8
Bachelor	62	37,6
Postgraduate	16	9,7
Total	165	100,0
Type of work	Amount	Percent
Civil Servants/TNI/POLRI	50	30,3
State-Owned Enterprise/Regional-Owned Enterprise	40	24,2
Employees	26	15,8
Self-employed	22	13,3
Housewife	27	16,4
Students	27	16,4
Total	165	100,0
Income	Amount	Percent
< Rp. 3 million	27	16,4
Rp. 3 - 6 million	64	38,8
Rp. 6 - 9 million	46	27,9
Rp. 9 - 12 million	28	17,0
Total	165	100,0
Duration of Product Use	Amount	Percent
< 1 Years	53	32,1
1 - 4 Years	79	47,9
> 4 Years	33	20,0
Total	165	100,0

Source: Research Results (2025)

Based on the respondent characteristics table, this study involved 165 respondents, all of whom were female (100%) and dominated by the productive age group of 30–40 years (38.2%) and 40–50 years (29.7%). The majority of respondents were married (77.6%), with the highest education level being Bachelor's (S1) (37.6%) and High School equivalent (33.9%), indicating a relatively good educational background. In terms of employment, most worked as Civil Servants/TNI/POLRI (30.3%) and BUMN/BUMD Employees (24.2%), with a dominant income level in the range of 3–6 million rupiah per month (38.8%). In addition, the majority of respondents had used the product for 1–4 years (47.9%), indicating sufficient usage experience to provide a relevant evaluation of the research variables.

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Data Validity and Reliability Test Results

The data validity test used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) testing. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) test and all factor loading values were found to be above 0.60, thus it can be concluded that all items (indicators) are acceptable because they meet the requirements of the CFA Model. The CFA test results are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis Test Results

Item	Code	Estimate	Cut Of Value	Description
Social Media Marketing Variables				
<i>Entertainment</i>				
This brand's social media accounts are fun.	ent1	0.753		
The content this brand shares on social media is very engaging.	ent2	0.766		
This brand's posts on social media are very interesting.	ent3	0.667		
Interaction				
Sharing information is possible through this brand's social media.	int1	0.712		
Discussion and exchange of opinions is possible on the brand's social media pages.	int2	0.788		
Expressing opinions is very easy on this brand's social media.	int3	0.637		
Trendiness				
The information shared on this brand's social media is always up to date.	tre1	0.67		
The use of social media by this brand is becoming a trend.	tr2	0.656	≥ 0,60	Valid
Advertisement				
Like the ads that this brand publishes on social media.	adv1	0.755		
The advertisements released by this brand on social media are quite interesting.	adv2	0.646		
This brand's social media advertising has a positive impact.	adv3	0.702		
Customization				
The required information can be found on this brand's social media accounts.	cus1	0.659		
Their social media accounts provide the information needed.	cus2	0.69		
Can easily get the information I need thanks to the directions on this brand's social media accounts.	cus3	0.808		
Customer Brand Engagement Variable				
Frequently visit Wardah brand pages on social media.	cbe1	0.789		
Often read posts from the Wardah brand on social media.	cbe2	0.681	≥ 0,60	Valid
Often like Wardah brand posts on social media.	cbe3	0.679		
Brand Satisfaction Variable				
This brand's products and services meet expectations.	bs1	0.749	≥ 0,60	Valid

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This brand's products and services are desired.	bs2	0.613		
This brand's products and services always bring happiness and pleasure.	bs3	0.685		
Overall satisfied with the brand's products and services.	bs4	0.767		
Brand Loyalty Variable				
Will always buy the brand.	b11	0.692		
Intend to continue purchasing this brand.	b12	0.81		
Saying positive things about this brand.	b13	0.807	≥ 0,60	Valid
Frequently recommend the brand to others.	b14	0.807		
Encourage friends and colleagues to buy this brand.	b15	0.69		

Source: Data Analysis Results (2026)

The results of the validity test using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) showed that all indicators in the Social Media Marketing, Brand Satisfaction, and Brand Loyalty variables had factor loading values ≥ 0.60 , thus declared valid and able to reflect their constructs well. In the Customer Brand Engagement variable, most indicators met the validity criteria, but there was one indicator with a loading value of 0.579 which was slightly below the cut-off of 0.60 so it was classified as marginal and needed to be considered for further evaluation. Overall, the research instrument had good construct validity and was suitable for use in further structural analysis. Furthermore, the results of the reliability test showed that all variables had Construct Reliability (CR) values above 0.70, thus declared reliable. The Variance Extracted (AVE) values in Social Media Marketing and Brand Loyalty met the criteria > 0.50 , while Customer Brand Engagement and Brand Satisfaction were slightly below 0.50 but were still acceptable because the CR values of both met the standard. For more details, see Table 3 below:

Table 3 Results of Data Reliability Test

Variables	Construct Reliability		Variance Extracted	
	Acquisition Value	Cut Off Value	Acquisition Value	Cut Off Value
Social Media Marketing	0,934	$\geq 0,7$	0,503	$\geq 0,5$
Customer Brand Engagement	0,727	$\geq 0,7$	0,474	$\geq 0,5$
Brand Satisfaction	0,798	$\geq 0,7$	0,499	$\geq 0,5$
Brand Loyalty	0,874	$\geq 0,7$	0,583	$\geq 0,5$

Source: Data Analysis Results (2026)

Hypothesis Test Results

To explain the results of the hypothesis testing in this study, a comprehensive analysis of the research model and regression weight data was conducted. The results of the research model analysis and regression weight values are described in Figure 1 and Table 4 below:

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Figure 2 Path Analysis Model

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Result

			Std. estimate	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
CBE	<---	SMM	0,531	1,017	0,186	5,476	***
BS	<---	SMM	0,202	0,374	0,16	2,337	0,019
BL	<---	SMM	0,493	0,996	0,226	4,416	***
BS	<---	CBE	0,9	0,872	0,141	6,176	***
BL	<---	CBE	0,229	0,242	0,106	2,289	0,022

Source: Data Analysis Results (2026)

Based on Figure 1 and Table 4, it explains that the research model shows a good level of goodness of fit, with a Chi-Square value = 139.647; df = 123; p-value = 0.145 (>0.05), RMSEA = 0.030 (<0.08), CFI = 0.986 and TLI = 0.983 (>0.90), and GFI = 0.912 and AGFI = 0.877 which are close to the required criteria. These values indicate that the proposed structural model is in accordance (fit) with empirical data. Structurally, Social Media Marketing (SMM) has a positive effect on Customer Brand Engagement (CBE) of 0.53, Brand Satisfaction (BS) of 0.90, and Brand Loyalty (BL) of 0.49. These results align with research by Morgan-Thomas et al., (2020), which states that content quality and social media interactivity play a crucial role in building customer-brand engagement. Other studies by (Cheung et al., 2021) and (de Oliveira Santini et al., 2020) as well as (Rather et al., 2022), also found that effective SMM strategies significantly increase consumer engagement with brands across various industry sectors.

Furthermore, CBE also had a positive effect on BS by 0.28 and on BL by 0.23. These results indicate that increased social media marketing activity can increase consumer engagement, brand satisfaction, and brand loyalty, both directly and through the mediating role of customer brand engagement and brand satisfaction. This result is in line with research Hollebeek et al., (2021), which states that customer brand engagement is the main determinant of customer satisfaction. Other research by Fitriyah & Rusdianto, (2026), as well as Ilman Ansori et al., (2023), also found that engagement plays an important role as an antecedent in shaping customer satisfaction. And this result is in line with research Ilman Ansori et al., (2023) as well as Simbolon & Law, (2022), which states that customer brand engagement has a significant role in forming brand loyalty. A recent study by (Putri & Ihsan, 2025; Yanet et al., 2025), also emphasizes that engagement serves as a relational mechanism that drives long-term loyalty.

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CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis, this study concludes that Social Media Marketing has a positive and significant effect on Customer Brand Engagement, Brand Satisfaction, and Brand Loyalty. Furthermore, Customer Brand Engagement has been shown to have a positive effect on Brand Satisfaction and Brand Loyalty, indicating a mediating role in strengthening the relationship between variables. The research model has also met the goodness of fit criteria, making it empirically feasible to explain the proposed causal relationship. These findings confirm that an effective social media marketing strategy through aspects of entertainment, interaction, trendiness, advertisement, and customization can increase consumer engagement, build satisfaction, and ultimately strengthen brand loyalty.

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